

THE APPLICATION OF VIDEO TRANSCRIPT IN ENGLISH CLASSES FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS: A SURVEY RESEARCH

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Abstract. *This research investigates medical students' perspectives on applying video transcripts in English classes on medical videos to enhance student learning, particularly in the vocabulary and terminology. This research used an experiment with 50 medical students of 1st year study in Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. The research aimed to explore whether using the transcribed texts before and after watching medical videos, can improve the vocabulary and lexicology of the given terminology. The findings from this study showed a significant level of student interest in studying transcripts before and after watching medical videos. As a result, their medical lexical comprehension was also affected by this study. Apart from watching the videos, the students also have been checked the terms and words of the transcribed texts available in tests and control dictionary works. This research shows that video transcripts that utilized in educational settings improve understanding and comprehension of study video material among medical students in general English practice.*

Keywords: *video transcript, English class, Medical students.*

Introduction. Despite the implementation of mandatory English classes during all eleven years school system in Uzbekistan, it may be possible that there has been little to no significant improvement in general English practice and comprehension. According to the 2022 PISA ranking released by OECD, (PISA 2022 Results - OECD) Uzbekistan is ranked 1055th out of 80 participating countries. Consequently, Uzbekistan has significantly lower levels of reading comprehension than other nations. This is further supported by the statement of Jumanova Sh. (2024) that Uzbekistan must establish a comprehensive understanding in English language through a systematic habituation, growth, and education process. M. Ingersoll (2017) recognized that importance of teacher training and professional development in improving educational outcomes have the potential to facilitate the acquisition of diverse abilities. This research highlights the necessity of specifically prioritizing the improvement of English professional comprehension.

Implementing technology in the classroom is a crucial objective that may be continuously evaluated to enhance the education system at all levels, in particular high levels of education. Henriksen et al. (2016) suggest that technology serves an important function in the process of learning. According to Alhomod, (2013) a most part of today's students depends greatly on their devices such as laptops, mobile phones and etc. Alhomod also stated that their primary use of technologies in the classroom is performing educative tasks, such as studying and completing tasks. Nevertheless, technology presents many problems that might limit the learning process.

The difficulties encountered in the learning process consist of 1). The limited utilization of smartphones as a medium for educational purposes, 2). Using educational materials still lags behind traditional methods and lacks engagement; 3). Additionally, there is a lack of appropriate learning material available (Novaliendry et al., 2020). Ultimately, this has the potential to result in students encountering ennui because of monotonous educational learning. English is an essential

method of communication in the context of global mobility (Setiawan & Nurbani, 2023). Therefore, the utilization of technology in English language acquisition, specifically in the main components of reading, writing, speaking, and listening, is crucial for achieving accomplishments. Watching study videos in the setting of all these components of English practice needs to be integrated with the goal of instruction and the variety of the students' backgrounds (Damaianti et al., 2020).

The results of contemporary technological advancements are significant. In TashPMI, the curriculum of the subject “English in medicine” employed is characterized by inflexibility and an excessive emphasis on content development of technology themselves (Buranova D.D., 2024). This study will examine the utilization of study technologies as an instructional platform for students’ learning. Based on Irwan et al., (2019) research, as additional study of technologies, video and audio materials, stated that a significant amount of video content from internet has become a fundamental component for students. (Setiadi et al., 2019) also said that the using of video materials is expected to be an alternative to creative learning. In several research studies, YouTube is one of the social media that has attracted a positive response from many quarters. Cited from Wijayanti & Gunawan (2021), the utilizing YouTube videos in English learning has increased students' enthusiasm for learning this course so that it is no more difficult for them to learn. Critical thinking skills, creativity, constructing and evaluating information, and effective use of digital media could all be developed due to students' digital writings (Al-Qallaf & Al-Mutairi, 2016). YouTube becomes content with the subject matter for professional learning of English language. Students search engaging video tutorials in a style related to vloggers. The students can benefit from the video's content, in particular medical ones. Beyond reaching the teaching-learning objective, people's projects as clinic activities or medical procedures can provide them with some knowledge and information that can benefit others. Medical topics contains various information since each issue is approached differently to the same general idea. Medical video has a variety of vocabulary and lexis based on how well they discuss the subject and how skilled they are.

The previous research utilized videos on medical topics and English for specific purposes (ESP) such as Listening and speaking (Albahiri & Alhaj, 2020). In addition, internet web-sites with medical topics provides an extensive variety of user-generated and focused professional videos. The popularity of it among medical students has consistently surged due to its wide range of functions and user-friendly. The staff of department “Foreign Languages” in TashPMI uses an online platform “Moodle” (mt.tashpmi.uz) that serves as a video archive, enabling anybody with internet connectivity to watch and upload medical videos for ESP. Consequently, there was a significant increase in both the understanding and realization of English medical videos among students. Therefore, authors tried to make the results of research on medical students' achievements in English classes in using transcriptions of medical videos. The aim is to know whether the medical student more readily understands the application of videos by presenting transcripts before and after watching video and can affect the student's learning outcomes. Therefore, the using of transcription before and after watching medical videos can be assessed better in English classes.

Materials and methods. The authors used the survey and analysis methods. The participants were first-year students of Pediatrics I and Therapy faculties in Tashkent Pediatric Medical Students in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Fifty respondents, 40 female and 10 male students in English classes answered on questions in the survey papers. They were divided in two groups, directed to watch English medical videos, the first of which had transcription before watching and the second

did not have transcription. The research instrument used in this study was a questionnaire survey. The questionnaire contained inquiries and statements about the independent and dependent variables formulated based on the issue. The participants were provided with an assignment of six questions to answer. The inquiries pertain to their inclination towards digital literacy, particularly in the context of medical English lexis comprehension. In addition, two distinct video samples were provided along with corresponding video references:

Video 1: Lesson 5 Human body (Human Body 101 | National Geographic).

Video 2: Lesson 12 Cardiovascular system II (Physiology of heart)

Data collection in this study involves collecting the participants in one class, and then the teacher will share the questionnaire papers, which will be accessed through each student's papers. After that, participants will answer the questions. The data will be processed and analyzed using MS Excel 2013 program. Students were invited to complete a survey at the end of the class. An hour was provided for the students to complete the questionnaire. The researcher will follow up on their responses during each participant's questionnaire submission.

Data analysis in this study used statistical data analysis, where this data collection used the percentage value obtained through the questionnaire. The data in this study used a validity test using a significance level (<0.05) with a correlation of $r > r$ table. The item score, factor score, and correlations between total factor scores are used in this validity test. In circumstances when the data are less than 0.05, the correlation coefficient (0.05) is found. The result is valid when the r calculated $\geq r$ table. Items that have a significant correlation with the general rating will indicate validity.

Table 1.1.

The questionnaire answers			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	50	100.0
	Excluded	0	0
Total		50	100.0

Table 1.2.

Data analysis statistics	
Significance level	Correlation
<0.05	$r > r$

Results and discussion. The primary purpose of writing this paper is to answer the question: How does the student's perception of the use of the application of transcript/subtitle on videos influence the English Lexis Comprehension of Medical Students? This study utilized six questions as a sample that would be asked to students directly. The results of the sample questions were then analyzed using the statistical data processing application of MS Excel 2013. The results of this study validity test confirm the validity of this research. The table below displays the results of the questionnaire test, which serves as evidence for the following statement:

Table 2.1.

Questionnaire Results

Questions	Group I		Group II	
	n	%	n	%
Q1	42	80%	48	90%
Q2	25	50%	45	88%
Q3	42	70%	30	60%
Q4	47	95%	40	78%
Q5	39	77%	18	40%
Q6	34	75%	15	37%

The questionnaire result shows that the validity indication is $r_{50} \geq 0.05$, which means the value of r is calculated $\geq r$ table and indicates a correlation to the application of medical video transcripts for students' lexis comprehension Based on Question 1, "What is Your Opinion on the Visual Appeal of the medical videos?"

The data shown in Table 2.2 indicate that students demonstrate an increased preference for movies that uses transcribed text before watching video compared with videos without transcribed text. Moreover, the Q2 posed was "Selecting the Video Sample That Received the Greatest Interest from Students?". The results indicated that students of the second group focused more on Video Sample 1, which featured video accompanied by amusing and captivating animations, despite the lack of transcribed text in the video. Refer to Table 2.3 to view a graphical depiction of the data.

Table 2.2.

Table 2.3.

Sample Video Transcript		
	Students	Percentage
Sample 1	7	23%
Sample 2	23	77%
Total	50	

The table above also illustrates the association between questions Q1 and Q2, which asked about the level of interest in using transcribed text before watching English medical videos. The findings suggest that students have a preference for the transcribed texts before watching video and express a low level of interest in videos without prescribed text. Additionally, Q3 follows the question: “Are you Interested in Videos That Have Subtitles? (Give your reasons if you are interested or not interested)”. Consequently, students provided a range of explanations for their increased attention to videos that included transcribed content.

Question Q4: What Rating Would You Assign to the Video Displayed Above? requested information regarding the scores of Sample Video 1 and Sample Video 2. The results suggest that the students gave positive evaluation scores for the video clip, averaging between 50% and 80%

Table 2.4

Score		
	Students	Percentage
1-50	8	10%
50-80	20	40%
80-100	22	50%
Others...	0	0%
Total	50	

Question 5: “How Do You Improve medical lexis in the Digital Age?” required students to solve the methods for enhancing medical English lexis in the modern era of technology. The results indicate an increased interest in the digital applications that students commonly utilize as a means

of learning Digital Literacy in the present era. Furthermore, the results are acquired as demonstrated in the table provided below.

Table 2.5

How to Improve Literacy in Digital Era		
	Students	Percentage
Reading Books	4	12%
Watching Videos	4	12%
Digital App	25	43%
Game	7	10%
Social Media	10	23%
Total	50	

Question 6: “What media do you usually use for ESP?” inquired about the primary media utilized for professional learning of English language. The outcomes are visible in the table provided below:

Table 2.6

How to Improve ESP		
	Students	Percentage
Youtube, Instagram, X, etc.	25	50%
Web-sites	15	40%
Others...	10	10%
Total	50	

Conclusion.

Human adjustment to technology is of the utmost importance in today's environment. The effects of modern advancements in technology can be recognized directly immediately. Previous research suggests that using additional abilities such as listening and speaking with the watching special videos may assist with improving professional English skills. The present research, for example, used professional lexis by utilizing the transcribed text from the video approach. This research aims to understand how digital media, an instructional teaching tool, affects on development of professional English comprehension. With the growing popularity of digital media as a learning tool, particularly for English language learning, the use of transcripts on video content is expected to assist teachers in creating a successful learning environment while encouraging students to learn as an alternative in the modern era. Transcription text on videos helps medical students simplify their learning, including medical lexis and vocabulary. Moreover, it can be helpful for students to create more opportunities for them to be creative and keep up with technological improvements. With the applications or something that can help students, they can be expected to increase motivation to study foreign languages in professional sphere. The reason is that when students recognize digital applications, they also have the opportunity to improve other skills than lexical comprehension—for example, writing skills and many others.

Students can improve their writing through digital applications that they use for lexical understanding. Students may additionally employ video games and online platforms to improve their understanding of professional vocabulary. Establishing lexis targets for learners can also involve using vocabulary-supporting apps such as Magoosh vocab, VocabWord Of The Day and others. The potential to improve vocabulary skills, especially for medical students, appears in the lexical content these applications may create.

The suggestion for further research is that other researchers can use this study's material in improving English teaching as reference material. Doing more research in digital technologies is possible for teachers and researchers in their future studies. The supporting applications mentioned may additionally be utilized as material for teachers and students of medical schools and colleges regarding using the media, which has also been studied in this research. The authors suggests that additional studies be done due to globalization of educative technologies since English is subject to professional development of every person. In particular, the accessibility of AI (Artificial Intelligence) gives it the potential to define issues for future research and studies in ESP.

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